

Designing Enhanced Robust 6G Connection Strategy with Blockchain

August Lykke Thomsen, Bastian Preisel, Victor Rodrigues Andersen,
Wei-Yang Chiu, and Weizhi Meng^(✉)

SPTAGE Lab, Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, Technical
University of Denmark, Denmark
{weich, weme}@dtu.dk

Abstract. With the rapid evolution of wireless communication technologies, the new generation of 6G is already under development, due to the next step-change in performance from Gigabit to Terabit capacities as well as reaching sub-millisecond response time. For example, 6G connectivity is expected to support speeds of one Terabyte per second. This level of capacity and latency will be in support of increasing demand in the areas of wireless cognition, detection and imaging. The 6G connection strategy is made to cope with the major traffic growth, especially in a crowded area, e.g., under celebration. However, without a proper connection strategy, an attacker can cause the traffic jam to one or more nodes in a 6G network. In this work, we consider the benefits of blockchain, and showcase a practical implementation of blockchain-enabled connection strategy for 6G, where telecom companies can use in order to provide the best connection experience and robustness for each device through connection strategies deployed on the chain. We also implement an Android application on mobile devices to demonstrate the viability of our approach.

Keywords: Blockchain technology, 6G, Connection strategy, Decentralized database, Smart contract, Blockchain application.

1 Introduction

The advancement of information technology creates method of communications more than verbal and physical, it creates multiple method of data transmission through several types of media. However, in the recent years of development, it has shown the trend of utilizing various medium to reach the final goal of the proposed communication system. For example, Long Term Evolution (LTE) [13] provides options for network operators to offload the data flow through local 802.11 access points, and later, LTE-M was released, as a suitable access media for Internet of Things (IoT), under the hood of LTE specification. Its successor, the New-Radio (NR) further branched the method of access detailly, such as Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) for critical applications that require real-time response and Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) for applications that need huge amounts of bandwidth.

It has no doubt that the later successor of 6G will have a similar system architecture [6]. It has become important to exploit the knowledge of different connection media types to provide the best user experience. For example, it is unreasonable for a 6G user to access a public macro-cell tower which can be quite packed, when the distributed femto-cells are deployed in / or near the residency that can provide faster response and better bandwidth-per-user ratio [1].

However, the current implementation of wireless devices is equipped with an elegant but not future-proof method of choosing the current access point, whichever shows the strongest signal toward the device, it will be the current access point of the device. Although such implementation can be reasonable when single media types were involved, it can be quite questionable when dealing with various medium and applications – The cell that shows the best reception does not always prove to have the best connection quality. Furthermore, based on different applications, several of its connections can be offloaded differently [7]. For example, a pre-recorded video can be transmitted through connections that have broader bandwidth but with slightly higher latency. Video and phone calls require real-time response, while bandwidth only has to be satisfiable to complete the task. Lastly, as the ubiquitous data access can be considered as the basic component of our daily life, the ability for dynamic and instant response toward the change of environment should be considered and included. For example, as congestions can be easily occurred during rush hours in packed areas, if operators can have the capability to provide reference guidelines for devices not to use the macro-cell tower by-default, such issue can be partially resolved.

Motivation. As the network operators have the full knowledge of their own networks, they are suitable for providing guidelines. However, the data distribution of these guidelines has become an issue since there are countless customers on the network. Having a centralized system may become costly for operators to maintain. Furthermore, as the deployment of connection strategy can heavily affect the user experience and system revenue, a system with high-availability and auditability is preferred. Blockchain proves itself as a better alternative compared with traditional database, since it satisfies the above requirements [4].

Contribution. Blockchain technology has been studied in various domains such as trust management [15,16], smart cities [3,17], intrusion detection [14], vehicular network [8,9], etc. It is a kind of distributed database that can be shared among nodes within a network, providing enhanced trust, security, transparency, and traceability of the data. Motivated by its benefits and the issues of connection strategy in 6G, in this work, we design and showcase a practical implementation of blockchain-enabled connection strategy scheme in 6G. Our contributions can be summarized as below:

- Typically, 6G allows devices to connect with a much wider variety of access medias, ranging from older cell towers to dedicated satellites and smaller cells. We design a blockchain-enabled 6G connection strategy for a more robust 6G environment, including smart contract design, client application design, web platform design, and Android App design.

- We then introduce how to implement the proposed strategy, based on an open-source blockchain development platform – DevLeChain, including user interface, workflow of the client class, and diagram of the client application. In the evaluation, we initially discuss the performance of our system, and demonstrate its viability.

The rest of the work can be summarized as follows. In Section 2, we briefly present the background of 6G and related work on blockchain-based 6G vision. Section 3 introduces the design of our blockchain-enabled 6G connection strategy. Section 4 details how to implement the system and strategy, and Section 5 discusses the system performance under several tests and use cases. Finally, we conclude the work in Section 6.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 6G Technology

6G is the sixth generation of wireless technology. A 6G network follows up on 4G and 5G, building on the revamped infrastructure and advanced capacity currently being established on millimeter-wave 5G networks. Using higher-frequency radio bands, it will give networks much faster speeds and lower latency, in order to support sophisticated mobile devices and systems [6]. It is anticipated that 6G networks will be able to use higher frequencies than 5G networks, which will enable higher data rates to be reached. This involves expanding into Tera-Hertz (THz) communications, due to its extremely short wave length, it becomes possible to meet the need for large-capacity short-distance communication, as well as high-precision positioning and sensing.

5G's many private wireless communication implementations involving LTE, 5G and edge computing for enterprise and industrial customers, have helped lay the groundwork for 6G [12]. Next-generation 6G wireless networks will further improve this and bring it to the next level. 6G technology is expected and envisioned to provide fully immersible interaction and support precise spatial interaction to meet the requirements for multiple senses, feeling, and mind communications. Communication for sensing and inclusive intelligence will realize the digitalization and intelligence of physical objects. Native intelligence, communication for sensing, digital twins, and native security are some of the key capabilities that 6G is planned to support.

Some of the other driving forces of 6G development are changes in social structure, since digital technologies are required to increase inclusiveness across unbalanced income levels and demographic imbalance calls for digital technology to improve human capital. High-quality economic growth is another critical aspect of its development, as sustainable economic growth is fueled by the impetus brought by new technologies, and the globalization of services requires lower cost in all-round information communications. Lastly, environmental sustainability also contributes to this scenario, given that lower carbon emissions and carbon neutrality call for improved energy efficiency and green development.

2.2 6G with Blockchain

Introducing blockchain technology to the 6G environment brings many beneficial features and characteristics to the system. Hewa *et al.* [18] introduced an intelligent resource management method that with the exponential expansion of the tenants future, the resource management operations such as spectrum sharing, orchestration and decentralized computation may require to be compatible with massive infrastructure volumes. They also mentioned the proposal of an intelligent network architecture, which utilized blockchain technology by handling the relationship between operators and users via smart contracts.

Wang *et al.* [20] introduced a Blockchain Radio Access Network for 6G (B-RAN). They described it as an open and unified framework for diverse applications to achieve resource pooling and sharing across sectors, which is an attractive solution for future 6G networks. B-RAN unites inherently untrustworthy network entities without any middleman, and it manages network access, authentication, authorization and accounting via trustful interactions. With B-RAN, a multi-sided platform (MSP) is established to connect different parties and facilitate resource and data sharing in a cooperative, flexible and secure way. B-RAN can not only dynamically share computing, caching and communicating capabilities, but also deliver and spread intelligence across subnetworks.

The 6G network is expected to be 3D integrated, such that we have 6G elements present in all three dimensions. This will help provide guaranteed Quality-of-Service (QoS). The 6G infrastructure will be made of dense deployment of communication devices, by operators or specialized asset service providers. By implementing the blockchain into the network, we can help reduce latency. Users will connect to a relay, and the relay will check the users' information and the network from the blockchain and provide the desired connectivity. It can be achieved by checking a smart contract, which contains the desired SLAs (Service-Level Agreement) made by the specialized service providers [11].

Other opportunities that come from implementing the blockchain with the 6G network can be summarized as below [21].

- Simplifying roaming terms and agreements between different providers.
- Helping the implementation of network slicing, by keeping track of how each resource is being used and how providers perform against the SLAs.
- Managing money transfers across borders.
- Managing users and authentication.

More related work on the combination of blockchain and 6G can refer to several recent studies [5,10,19,22]. To the best of our knowledge, there is no prior work discussing how to use blockchain technology to optimize and secure connection strategies in 6G era. This motivates our work on implementing a prototype of blockchain-enabled 6G connection strategy.

3 Our Proposed System

The main goal of our work is to deploy and maintain connection strategies for telecommunication companies in a 6G environment, and validate the feasibility

and viability of this approach. Fig. 1 describes the overview of system design. The system can interact with a private Ethereum-based blockchain, by integrating **Ethers** with the **Web3j** Ethereum APIs and libraries. The design also involves a web application that retrieves and sends information through a smart contract running on a private blockchain and an end-user application retrieving this information and acting accordingly.

Based on this design, telecom companies can have an easily accessible platform to deploy, manage and visualize the deployed strategies. The end-user application may vary from device to device as there might be different versions on which the device is running, such as smartphone, computer or cell server. While it allows the rest of the system to remain untouched and consistent throughout the entire network. This also provides reliable, secure and consistent data across the setup given that it is built up on blockchain technology.

Fig. 1. Overview of the system design

3.1 Smart-Contract Design

When designing a smart contract, we need to consider what kind of strategy should be involved in terms of fields and relevant information. First, we need a field to store what type of **connection** should be used, such as Wi-Fi, Satellite or Cellular. This field would have the main responsibility for what action has to be performed when it is active. Then we need to decide a strategy to hold the **dates** regarding when the strategy is active. We also need to choose a strategy with a **priority** value to decide which of the strategies with overlapping time frames should be the active one.

In addition, we also need a strategy to hold a **location** where it should be active. This means that the device would have to be in the given area defined by

the location in order for the strategy to become active. A **location** is composed of **latitude** and **longitude** coordinates for the center of a circle, along with a **radius**, in order to define a circular area for each strategy. This could be relevant if a user is in an area where people are usually outside in large crowds, where a lot of traffic to the nearest cell tower could overload it. To round it out, a strategy should also have a **name** and a **description**. Every strategy also has a unique **ID**.

In order to pass the information to the client devices, when a new strategy has been added, we decided to use events provided by Solidity. These events will broadcast to all devices connected to the blockchain and the contract. In our case, an event is emitted whenever a change has been made to the array, i.e., being the addition of a new strategy, removal of one, or a change in priority. This signals that a re-evaluation of the array is needed at each device in order to figure out which strategy has to be active among the new constellation.

3.2 Client Application Design

When designing the client application, we select Java as the programming language as it can integrate with Ethereum blockchain with the **Web3j** library. The client application should retrieve the currently deployed strategies and decide which one of them should be active. For this purpose, it should have a function to retrieve the strategies array and assign it to a global data structure in the application. After that, there should be a method to choose which strategy should be active. This involves iterating through the list of strategies, checking its start and end date along with the priority and location. Given that there was no active strategy prior to such check, the one that meets the former conditions should be the chosen one. Should there be two or more that apply for the given date and location, the one with the highest priority will be chosen in the end. Also, should two strategies have the same priority, the first one encountered will be chosen.

Once the strategy is chosen, it has to be enabled. Thus, the application needs a function that performs the necessary changes on the device in order to suit the chosen strategy. This may vary from device to device, while in our case, it will include the code needed to enable or disable a Wi-Fi or Bluetooth interface on a Linux distribution either on a laptop or a Raspberry Pi. Then a listener is needed to the event that is emitted every time a change is made to the strategy list. Should the event be triggered, it fetches the list again and runs the same process described before. Other than the event listener, the application checks periodically whether the current active strategy is expired or not valid for the current location; in that case, it should choose a new one if there is a fit with the new location and time.

3.3 Web Platform Design

The motivation for having a web platform is to be able to manage the deployed strategies, especially the deployment and the deletion. The platform also serves

the purpose of providing an overview of which strategies are currently deployed, in what location, and their additional information, such as start- and end-time. This will be useful for the people responsible for this on the company side.

One of the essential design choices is to include a map, which can display the current strategies and their locations. This allows users to have an easy overview of the strategies. However, only having a map to display the strategies can easily become unmanageable, as strategies can overlap each other. Therefore we decided to also have a grid displaying the strategies in addition to a map. Displaying the map and the grid beside each other will then allow users to easily create an overview of all the strategies on the blockchain.

3.4 Android App

Having a smartphone version also allows us to work with a different environment and make use of different parameters when deciding which strategy should be active. Also, providing the client's computer with current location is a challenge; thus, having a smartphone version allows us to include this easily in the code that is already made for the computer application.

The design consists of two pages. The first one is where the user sets up the information to connect to the blockchain such as IP, port and so on, as well as the information for the account to be used, such as the key file and password. Once this is properly inserted and a connection has been established, the second screen is shown, which displays the current state of the system, i.e., the current active strategy, or that no strategy is active at the current time.

4 System Implementation

4.1 Blockchain

To communicate with the blockchain, we need to connect to an Ethereum node. In this work, we used the JSON-RPC protocol to interact, which allows us to execute code on another machine. JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) is a lightweight data-interchange format, which can represent numbers, strings, ordered sequences of values, and collections of name/value pairs. Combining JSON and RPC (Remote Procedure Call), it can communicate with the blockchain, where the blockchain acts as a server deployed on a network, and the clients use the JSON-RPC protocol to make changes on the blockchain.

The blockchain platform was developed based on DevLeChain [2], which can provide various functions, i.e., creating a new local chain with multiple accounts. We could also start peering multiple nodes with each other, by having two nodes with the same genesis file and network ID, but having different ports. We could add them as peers using the JavaScript command – `admin.addPeer(enode)` in the Geth console. The enode is viewable by using `admin.nodeInfo`. We could also peer two nodes from two different computers over the same network, by changing the IP in the `enode`.

Fig. 2. UML diagram of smart contract

4.2 Smart Contract

Programming in Solidity using Remix IDE was the most optimal choice since it is a combo of an object-oriented programming language designed to implement smart contracts. RemixIDE also allows smart contracts to be easily tested as functions, which can be called directly from the user interface, and it also allows testing by deploying the contract on JavaScript VMs available within the IDE, instead of setting up own chain and deploying it.

Fig. 2 depicts a diagram of the smart contract. A **Strategy** was implemented including a *struct* containing the fields, with the **Location struct** that includes **latitude** and **longitude** coordinates as 32 byte integers, and a **radius** that is the same size but unsigned. The **id** is also an unsigned integer, alongside the **startDate** and **endDate** for the strategy in question. The dates are stored as UNIX timestamps. The **ConnectionType** and **Priority** were implemented as **enums** in order to have predefined constants that can be chosen from, in this case being (**DATA**, **WIFI**) and (**LOW**, **MEDIUM**, **HIGH**) respectively.

Then the **name** and the **description** fields were both implemented as **bytes32**, meaning that they were byte arrays instead of regular Strings. This has to be done because **Web3j** is used for the client application, which cannot handle and generate proper data structures and methods for Solidity **Strings**, due to the dynamic size.

As global fields for the contract, there is an **id** integer in order to keep track of unique ids given to each strategy, the address of **owner** to commit changes to the strategies and add or remove them. The global **id** counter is initialized to 0 and only incremented by 1 every time when a strategy is added, indicating that new strategies will have a unique ID never used, not even by strategies that have been deleted. This also means that a maximum of strategies that can be

made during the lifetime of the contract, since the ID is a `uint256`. This means there is a max amount of $2^{256} - 1$ strategies that can be created.

When it comes to the functions the smart contract is also composed of, we first have the methods related to the owner of the smart contract: `isOwner()` to check whether the *callee* is the owner of the contract, `updateOwner()` to update the owner of the contract and `getOwner()` to return the address of the owner. In order to add or remove strategies from the list, we implemented `makeStrategy()` and `deleteStrategy()`. The first one takes all the necessary parameters formerly described that a strategy has and creates the struct, pushes it into the array, increments the global ID counter and emits the event broadcasting a change in the strategy list. The `deleteStrategy()` method deletes a strategy from the list by given its ID.

Should a situation arise where the company has to change the **priority** of a strategy in order to activate it because some conditions changed or because another should take its place, we decided to implement a `changePriority()` function that takes the index of the strategy whose priority should be changed, and sets the priority to the new value.

The smart contract should also naturally allow users and clients to connect to it, aiming to retrieve the information stored. For that purpose, the functions `getStrategies()` and `getStrategyFromIndex()` have been implemented. The first one simply returns the list of strategies in its current state, while the second one returns a strategy object given an index from the list.

4.3 Web Platform

To communicate with the blockchain, we used the `ethers.js` library, which handles interaction with the blockchain and its ecosystem. We also used this library to set up the JSON-RPC connection to the blockchain.

Fig. 3. User interface for viewing the current strategies on the blockchain

Fig. 4. User interface for adding a new strategy to the blockchain

The component that shows the current strategies is shown in Fig. 3. As mentioned in Section 3.3, it contains a map and a grid, where the map shows the location of the strategies, and the grid contains other details about the strategies. The grid uses the `react-grid-layout` package, in order to dynamically change the grid.

The strategies displayed on the map are color-coded based on their priority, where green is low, yellow is medium, and red is high. The edge color is also color-coded, based on whether the strategy is active, inactive, or expired, with the colors orange, black, and purple respectively. If a strategy is selected, it will display information about the clicked strategy.

The grid changes, depending on what strategies are currently on the blockchain, where each item on the grid corresponds to a strategy. The color of each strategy on the list is color-coded the same way as the edge color of the strategies. This makes it more intuitive for the user. Each strategy then has a button labeled ‘details’, which displays additional information in a popup modal, such as its description, and an ‘X’ in the top-right corner to remove it from the blockchain.

To update the map and grid displaying the current strategies, an event listener was made to listen for when new blocks were added on the blockchain. When a new block is added to the blockchain, the map and grid will fetch the strategies from the contract again, this time from the newest block. Fig. 4 shows how the user can upload a strategy to the blockchain. It contains a map and a form, where the map allows users to mark an area for the strategy to be added, and a form containing the details of the strategy to be added. The fields are: name, priority, description, connection type, start-date, start-time, end-date, and end-time. All of the fields are necessary to deploy a strategy to the blockchain, except for the description field. Also, it requires a valid address as the sender and a marked area to deploy a strategy to the blockchain. If one or more of the required information is missing, a popup will inform the user.

Fig. 5. Expired strategy with invalid address

The navigation-bar contains links to the other parts of the page, an input field which takes the address of the user and also displays the last address entered. This address is used for transactions on the blockchain, i.e., adding or removing a strategy. This address is saved in the computer's local storage, so it will be saved when the page is closed or refreshed.

We can also remove the expired strategies, as shown in Fig. 5, which can be done automatically by removing the expired strategies when the website is rendered, if the user has entered a valid address as the one calling the `deleteStrategy()` method from the smart contract. If not, the expired strategies will be displayed as expired, until the user enters a valid address.

4.4 Client Application

As mentioned in 3.2, the client application was implemented in Java and with a wide use of the `Web3j` blockchain library. `Web3j` is a Java and Android library for working with Smart Contracts and integrating with clients (nodes) on the Ethereum network. It allowed us to work with the Ethereum blockchain, without the additional overhead of having to write our own integration code for the platform.

As shown in Fig. 6, the application is divided in classes where the **Client** class is the main class, responsible for all the logic of how the strategies are handled and all the others are support classes storing information and providing functions ranging from interactions with the contract to credentials storage.

To achieve the defined goals for the **Client** class, three particular functions such as `setStrategies()`, `chooseActiveStrategy()` and `enableStrategy()` were implemented. Other than these, the class also contains the `main()` method. The file also keeps track of the stored information by having a **Strategy** object `active_strategy`, which holds the currently active strategy, an object for the

contract itself, and the list of strategies at its current state. The first function mentioned is responsible for retrieving the strategy array from the smart contract, and assigning the global list stored in the program, by calling the `getStrategies()` function in the generated contract class by Web3j. The function `enableStrategy()` is the one responsible for running the code that will interact with the operating system or host device, in order to execute the necessary commands to match the chosen strategy; mainly by looking at its `ConnectionType` value.

Fig. 6. Workflow of the client class

The workflow of the program starts with creating the contract object, and then a list of strategies is retrieved and a check is run to decide which should be the active one. Once it is completed, should there be an active strategy, it is then enabled and the device settings are tweaked in order to suit it. Then the event listener thread is created, which will keep listening for an event trigger when a change has been made to the list. As soon as that happens, the process of retrieving, choosing, and enabling strategies is run once again, and finally the thread waits again for another trigger. After the creation of the thread, an infinite loop is initiated so that a check can be made every 10 seconds to explore whether the current strategy is expired or time has come for a new strategy to be the active one. This is done by running the `chooseActiveStrategy()`

Fig. 7. Diagram of the Client application

method to figure out which strategy should be active. If the returned object is different than the current one, a change should be made, and the new one is set to be active and enabled through `enableStrategy()`. Once it has been done, the program loops and sleeps for 10 seconds again before running another check.

Another class was the `ContractCreator`, whose job is to establish the connection between the client application, the smart contract, and the contract object itself, which will be used and interacted in the `Client` class.

Its code is primarily built by Web3j objects and functions, in order to set up the connection with the blockchain network, a series of steps need to be followed so that the contract can be loaded. The **address** of the contract on the chain has to be stored and a `HttpService` has to be created based on the IP address and port number that the chain has as endpoint. Thereafter a new account is created by generating a new key pair of public and private key, followed by a wallet as well. In our implementation, a new account is made every time when the program is running again, but in a real network, it would only be created if there is no account already created on the running device. The credentials are then used to create a `RawTransactionManager` followed by the creation of a `DefaultGasProvider` object as well.

The `SixG_Strategy` class is also a major component of the application, which contains all the functions that correspond to the ones in the smart contract. However it is automatically generated by the Web3j package when being given the `.abi` file for the compiled contract alongside its binary code in a `.bin` file. Thereafter the package generates all functions, event listeners and classes, so that everything in the smart contract is accessible in Java in a class of its own. The diagram of the client application is depicted in Fig. 7.

Fig. 8. Class Diagram of the App

4.5 Android App

Fig. 8 illustrates the class diagram of the App design. We have two Android activities: the start activity to input connection data, and the main `ConnectedActivity`, which runs after connecting to the node. The `ContractCreator` class holds a method that takes the necessary arguments, and creates a `Web3j` object by using an HTTP service to the given URL. This returns a `SixG.Strategy` that is a subclass of the Web3j's `Contract` class, and is generated by Web3j's command line interface.

The `StrategyFinder` class implements the `Runnable` interface, so that it can run in the background without stopping the UI thread. It is responsible for retrieving the strategies on the contract, and finding the most suitable one. It holds a list of `Strategies`, which is a java representation of the `struct` in the contract, automatically created by Web3j. It runs a loop that checks the strategies in the list every 10 seconds and updates the list every time when the contract calls `StrategyChangedEvent`.

The map fragment is a subclass of an Android fragment, which is attached to the `ConnectedActivity`. It holds a `GoogleMap` field, and with the methods of `setCircle()` and `removeCircle()`, we can show the area where the active strategy is valid. We used the class `DummyConnection` to symbolize the change of connection method. The class contains `setConnection(int connectionType)`, where the argument is corresponding to the `connectType` enum in the smart contract. This method can be changed in the future, in order to support changing the connection type of our mobile data.

5 Evaluation and Discussion

As a case study, we implemented unit tests and run different testing frameworks for each component of the system, since each was implemented in its own programming language and environment. For example in the case of testing the smart contract, RemixIDE has a built-in unit testing tool, which can generate a generic test file that can be expanded and customized to implement the tests for our contract.

We then programmed unit tests for the methods implemented in the smart contract. Mainly `makeStrategy()`, `deleteStrategy()` and `changePriority()`. For the case of the first function, we tested whether the strategy was actually added to the list and with the correct given ID. For the second function we tested with a check whether the length of the new list is less than the previous one, meaning not only that the strategy was deleted but the size of the array was also dynamically changed. For the `changePriority()` test, we issued a check whether the new priority is the same of the one that the method was called on the list. The performance and correctness of the smart contract was also tested in the overall tests we did on the system.

When it came to testing the client application, we decided to bundle the tests with the Android app, since the logic is exactly the same, apart from location checks on the Android version. The most important aspect to be tested was the process of choosing which strategy has to be chosen from the list. Thus, we made a unit test for the app, by checking the logic for the `chooseActiveStrategy()` method. This is because it contains a large boolean logic check. The tests we performed can be summarized as below.

- No strategies are uploaded (an empty list is received).
- A strategy that should get applied or added.
- Going from one strategy to one with higher priority.
- A strategy that is expired gets added.
- Applying a strategy that later expires, and then choosing a strategy with lower priority.
- A strategy that far away gets added.

In order to test the overall performance of the system, manual tests had to be performed as there was no unified unit testing framework that we could work with, which suited every platform and application of the system we implemented. For this reason, we came up with different scenarios in which the program should behave as expected. We added the following use cases.

- No strategy is on the list and a strategy is added that should instantly become active.
- No strategy is active and we reached `startDate` for a strategy on the list. Meaning it should be activated.
- The active strategy expires and no other is valid for the time being.
- A strategy is currently active but another has been added valid for the same time as the current one, but with higher priority.

- A strategy with high priority expires but another with lower priority is still valid.
- A strategy that is currently active is deleted but another is still valid.
- A strategy that is currently active is deleted but there is no other on the list.

Observations and Results. In all these cases, the system behaved as expected and in the correct way according to our goals. For example, Fig. 9 shows that our app can correctly display the strategy status. When it comes to the performance and efficiency, the system depends mainly on the amount of time it takes to mine each transaction, as the event trigger is instant as soon as the transaction has been mined, initiating the selection process in the client application.

Fig. 9. The test for exploring the strategy. (a) No strategy is used, and (b) A strategy is being used.

Discussion. After setting up the blockchain, the platform run smoothly as a whole, and the response time was reasonable from the moment a change is committed from the web platform to the client application reacted, by considering the mining process the transaction has to go through. From the client application's perspective, the worst case scenario is only dependent on the time it takes for a transaction to finish being mined, given how as soon as that happened, the event listener is triggered, starting the entire strategy selection process as

previously mentioned, meaning that it has nothing to do with the `while` loop checking for strategy validity. The latter on the other hand, has a worst case scenario when a strategy expires or another should become active, just as the loop enters the 10 second sleep-period and then has to unnecessarily wait that time before it performs the changes needed. This means that the device can lose 10 seconds of optimal connection but given how strategies probably have a period of at least a few hours rather than days or months, then 10 seconds is not significant for the end user.

6 Concluding Remarks

The connection strategy is important to ensure the 6G performance, such as real-time response according to the change of environment. However, traditionally centralized schemes are expensive with low-availability, low-adaptivity, and low-auditability. In this work, we explored the use of blockchain for a more robust connection strategy and provided a practical implementation of blockchain-enabled connection strategy in 6G era. The main goal of our work was to assess the viability of using blockchain to control the connectivity of a network through connection strategies applied to diverse devices on the grid in 6G. In our test, the results demonstrated the viability of our proposed system.

Further, our proposed system can also be used in a way that the clients can provide information about the quality of the connection currently in a certain location to the smart contract and the telecommunications company in a way that a strategy can be made activated according to the information gathered. It means that a large amount of data on the connectivity can be gathered from several clients, which can generate something like a map of the connection quality for different places, in order to help everyone involved for achieving a better and more robust connection.

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